

Bradford HDRC Policy Brief

Improving children's oral health with and through education settings

Target Audience: Local Authorities

Based on N8 Child of the North Report - An evidence-based plan for improving children's oral health with and through education settings
Health_Report_8.pdf

Key Evidence Based Messages

- **Poor oral health affects quality of life.** It causes pain, sleep disruption, and impacts on speech and confidence.
- **Tooth decay is distributed unequally.** Children in deprived areas are two and a half times more likely to have decayed teeth.
- **National level focus:**
 - Develop a National Child Oral Health Improvement Strategy Focussing on reducing sugar consumption, optimizing fluoride exposure and increasing access to dental care.
 - Reorient Dental Services towards prevention and reform the national dental contract.
- **Local level focus:**
 - Maximise early years and education-based interventions and implement oral health components in public health services and school curricula.
 - Develop local oral health strategies that deliver interventions that are locally coproduced, based on the needs of local populations and focussed on vulnerable populations.
 - Build on approaches trialled in practice, highlighted in this briefing.

The Problem: Poor Oral Health

3 in 10 five year olds have tooth decay

4 in 10 twelve year olds are embarrassed by their teeth

5 in 10 children have visited a dentist in the last year

Hospital admissions for decay related tooth extractions cost the NHS over £40 million every year. Tooth decay causes toothache, sleepless nights and altered eating habits in children. It can also impact negatively on speech and language development, lower confidence, and lead to poor school attendance and performance. It has an impact on the wider family, causing lack of sleep and time off work.

What you can do at a local level

- **Develop a local oral health strategy.** This should link with other local strategies, for example healthy weight and nutrition strategies that will have similar goals such as reducing sugar intake. The strategy should be based on local population need underpinned by needs assessments.
- **Ensure oral health is a core part of local delivery of services** such as the Healthy Child Programme, Family Hubs, Healthy Schools Programmes.
- **Develop partnerships across sectors** to leverage in resources, expertise and support flexible commissioning.
- **Work with local communities** to identify local needs and develop projects and programmes in community settings.
- **Work with schools** to extend and enhance supervised toothbrushing and training of staff.

Approaches trialled in practice

Example	Approach	Impact
Sugar reduction programmes e.g. Blackpool GULP or Sheffield's Sweet Enough	Development of coproduced local assets to support children and families to reduce sugar consumption. Assets used by multiple partners including the business sector across a place.	Educate and inform parents and young people and support a reduction in the amount of sugar consumed.
ToothPASTE	Programme designed specifically to support children with autism to have better oral health, co designed with children and families. Also provides training across different early years professionals to enable them to be confident to provide support.	Addresses specific oral health challenges faced by children with autism and empowers professionals and parents to support young people with oral health.
The Westend food bank, Newcastle	A partnership between dental staff and students and the food bank to provide a dental check and fluoride varnish or silver diamine application to children attending the food bank. Provided a safe environment for children and families to engage with dental staff.	Provide preventative treatment there and then to children, as well as onward referral where a need was identified.
Child friendly dental practices	An alternative pathway for children referred to the paediatric dental service, particularly when there were long waiting times for the specialist service.	Child friendly dental practices offering quicker and more local access to children.
HABIT (Health Visitors delivering Advice in Britain on Infant Toothbrushing)	An online resource coproduced by parents and Health Visitors to support professionals and parents. Aimed at supporting those for whom English is an additional language.	Educate and inform parents on how to look after their children's teeth. Provide resources for health visitors to have conversations and support parents in oral health promotion.
BRIGHT (Brushing RemInder 4 Good oral Health)	A behavioural change resource for 11-13 year olds which can be delivered as part of the Key Stage 3 PHSE programme.	Improve the quality and quantity of toothbrushing in secondary school pupils.
BRUSH (optimising tooth Brushing Programmes in nurseries and Schools)	A toolkit that brings together good practice and resources that can be downloaded and adapted for the local context to help support the implementation of supervised toothbrushing programmes and clubs.	Increase the number and quality of supervised toothbrushing programmes in local areas.